

Vibration of angle-ply conical shells with linear and exponential variation in thickness

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Abstract: The study of conical shells enables the engineers to meet the demand of industries. A number of analytical and numerical studies have been conducted on the static and free vibration analysis of conical shells. Free vibration of truncated conical shell with variable thickness by using of the transfer matrix approach was analyzed [1,2].

Keywords: conical shells, static and free vibration, eigenfrequencies, eigenvectors, thickness variation.

In this study, free vibration of laminated conical shell frusta of variable thickness is analyzed using spline approximation. This spline approach was studied in [2,3]. The shells are considered as antisymmetric angle-ply orientation and the first order shear deformation is included in this problem. The governing differential equations of the shells are resolved in terms of displacement functions and rotational functions. These functions are approximated using splines as

$$\begin{aligned}U(X) &= \sum_{i=0}^2 a_i X^i + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} b_j (X - X_j)^3 H(X - X_j); \\V(X) &= \sum_{i=0}^2 c_i X^i + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} d_j (X - X_j)^3 H(X - X_j); \\W(X) &= \sum_{i=0}^2 e_i X^i + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} f_j (X - X_j)^3 H(X - X_j); \\ \Psi_X(X) &= \sum_{i=0}^2 g_i X^i + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} p_j (X - X_j)^3 H(X - X_j); \\ \Psi_\Theta(X) &= \sum_{i=0}^2 l_i X^i + \sum_{j=0}^{N-1} q_j (X - X_j)^3 H(X - X_j); \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

and the method of collocation is adopted to bring into the simultaneous algebraic equations. These equations become as generalized eigenvalue problem and is defined as

$$[P][q] = \Lambda[Q][q] \quad (2)$$

which is solved numerically to avail eigenfrequencies and the corresponding eigenvectors. The variation of frequencies are analysed with respect to the cone angle, aspect ratio, material properties, number of layers and thickness variation.

References

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